

RUNNING HEAD: DEBATE AND POSTSECONDARY EDUCATORS

The impact of prior experience in intercollegiate debate upon a postsecondary educator's skill-set.

Abstract:

This paper reports the results of a pilot survey of postsecondary educators who participated in intercollegiate policy debate. Open-ended and Likert scale items elicit educators' perceptions of whether the lessons they learned from competitive debate helped or hurt their work in the classroom, and in what way and measure. Results suggest that former debaters who work in the classroom benefit from their research skills, their seasoning as public speakers, and their ability to think on their feet, but suffer from speaking too rapidly and being too argumentative.

The assumption that successful debaters belong in law school is widespread, but Matlon & Keele's (1984) survey of NDT alumni indicates that teaching rivals law practice as a post-debate career. Two major motivators that drive excellent students to become educators are prior experience with intensive research and public recognition for their academic accomplishments (Lindholm, 2004). For those who teach K-12, there is training in the mechanics of instruction, and student teaching hones their debate-developed communication abilities into the necessary skill-set for classroom teaching. But those who pursue an advanced degree to teach postsecondary students, often enter their first classroom with nothing more than content knowledge, a few tips from a colleague, a class roster, and whatever talents they possessed before they entered graduate school (Reybold, 2003; Feldhusen et al., 1998; Wolverton, 1998).

Little has been written about debate experience as preparation for a career in postsecondary education; yet, the foundations of such research have been laid in broader inquiry into postsecondary teaching. University teachers should help students recognize complete, cogent arguments (Bain, 2004), should have excellent organization and oral communication skills (Chesebro, 2003), and should speak bluntly when students produce sub-standard work (Fram & Pearse, 2000). Cros (2001) asserts that most classroom communication events are best understood as argument. Colbert (2003) finds that participation in policy debate increases argumentativeness, while Schrod (2003) finds at least a modest link between argumentativeness and credibility with students.

The relationship between debate experience and success as a university educator merits further study. Reybold (2003) argues that the preexisting academic culture from which professors emerge is the key to understanding the variance in teaching quality from classroom to classroom. And debate program directors clearly would benefit from an understanding of what elements of debate experience might be emphasized, downplayed, or altered for students who show promise

as future educators. Such efforts could become a potent argument in justifying the continued existence of their programs, an argument that would hit very close to home for university administrators faced with tight resource constraints.

Because virtually no research exists on the effect of past debate experience on educators' classroom behaviors, this is a pilot study whose purpose is to lay groundwork for future studies by identifying particular topics of interest, both positive and negative, to educators who once debated. The items were written to elicit from the educators themselves the variables to be examined in later research.

Method

Participants

Calls for participants were posted to the eDebate and CRTNET listservs in February and March of 2005. The calls specified that subjects should have competed in intercollegiate policy debate at a time when it was evidence-intensive and involved rapid delivery, that they should have reached a level of minimum competence, operationalized as a normal performance of no worse than three wins out of eight preliminary debates, or two out of six preliminary debates, in an open-division tournament. It finally specified that they should currently be working as college educators, but *not* as debate coaches. Those who responded to the call were emailed a URL which led to the informed consent briefing, and then to the survey. Participants were further screened with an introductory question which asked them to describe their three most significant accomplishments in intercollegiate debate.

One hundred and twenty-six people responded, and one hundred and eight unspoiled responses were collected. Thirty participants were female and seventy-eight male. Seventy taught in the field of Communication, seventeen in Law, and the remaining twenty-one in other fields¹.

¹ 9 in Political Science, 3 in Philosophy, 2 in International Relations, and 1 each in Community College Education, Economics, History, Cognitive Science, Management, Math, and Sociology.

Number of academic terms' experience as an educator varied, with the bottom quartile ranging from one to eleven terms taught, and the top from 35 to 74 terms taught.

Procedures

Participants responded both to open-ended questions and Likert-scale items, which invited them to describe ways in which their experience in debate had influenced their in-class effectiveness as educators. Open-ended and Likert items were on separate web pages, with a "submit" click between each set, so that the stems of the Likert items would not contaminate participants' reports of their own perceptions.

Instruments and measures

The first open-ended prompt asked for *positive* influences: "Please describe the ways, if any, you believe your participation in debate helped prepare you to work as an educator. List, describe and discuss skills, habits, personality traits, or any other changes in you, brought on all or in large part by debate participation, which made the job easier." Completing this prompt and submitting it took participants to a set of twenty-one Likert scale items which probed for agreement with statements describing their own teaching behaviors, attributing those behaviors to past experience in debate, and agreeing that those behaviors enhanced their effectiveness in the classroom. The seven behaviors were thinking one one's feet, teaching both sides of controversial issues, allotting classroom time effectively, handling student disruptions in a confident fashion, taking in large volumes of information by listening, carrying out labor intensive preparation and grading tasks very efficiently, and thinking through student responses to changes in policy and procedure.

The second open-ended item elicited descriptions of *negative* influences past debate experience had on participants' teaching behaviors. The prompt replaced "helped prepare you to work" with "undermines your work," changed "habits" to "bad habits," and replaced "easier" with

"more difficult." The second set of Likert items probed for agreement with descriptions of negative traits and behaviors, including impatience, arguing excessively with students because of competitive instinct, speaking rapidly, having unrealistic expectations of student abilities or preparation, indulging in tangents for the enjoyment of pursuing an argument, dominating class discussion from a love of talking, and being abrasive with students.

Results

Open-ended question responses

The overwhelming answer to the first question on benefits of debate experience for teacher preparation was research. Sixty-four participants cited it as a benefit, with thirty-one mentioning it first. Some comments linked this to teaching: "The ability to go to the library (or online) and get up-to-date information on virtually any subject has made keeping my course current a much easier job. Also, when I have been "asked" to teach outside my specific areas of interest/expertise, I have been able to read-up much more rapidly than my colleagues." Others tied it to publication for professional advancement: "While the process of getting books, articles, and conference papers published is rigorous, those reviewers are not nearly as tough as my debate opponents were." A second freestanding response that was striking in its frequency was the introduction to the subject matter participants now teach: 21 responses indicated that the participant chose their academic field, or their particular area of study, after first encountering it through debate. One reported, "As a history major, debate was my entry into the field of Communication and helped prepare me for a[n] MA and Ph.D in Speech Communication." Another commented, "High-school and college debate taught me academic research skills; it also introduced me to writings in the academic study of IR, social theory, and other disciplines I draw upon in my current scholarly activities."

The other responses can be grouped into three broad categories: effective teaching

behaviors, generating and structuring knowledge, and cultivating personal traits. *Teaching behaviors* included delivery skills (mentioned in 45 responses), managing time effectively (25 responses), being fast on one's feet (17 responses), being prepared to teach students how to argue (9 responses), using language effectively (8 responses), having a wealth of examples from past debate research (7 responses), fielding questions (6 responses), anticipating student questions (5 responses), and handling discipline problems (2 responses). "As a teacher, I am well organized, well informed, well spoken, and quick in the classroom. My students enjoy my classes and are often awed with my quick analysis or answer to their questions." Four participants reported that summer clinics or peer coaching experiences were their first opportunities to teach.

Generating and structuring knowledge chiefly includes organizational skills (39 responses) and making arguments to students, to administrators, to colleagues (37 responses), but also includes analyzing others' arguments (25 responses), thinking critically (21 responses), being a problem-solver (9 responses), writing clearly (8 responses), thinking conceptually and seeing relationships between ideas (6 responses), and taking notes (5 responses). "I learned to think about writing, teaching, speaking as making arguments. I learned analytic skills that are useful in my teaching and research--how to break down or see problems in someone else's argument or my own, how to substantiate claims, how to identify what's missing."

Personal traits that former debaters reported they had cultivated included being more confident (44 responses), being open-minded enough to see and understand two or more opposing sides in a controversy (21 responses), being self-disciplined (7 responses), teamwork (8 responses), making durable friendships (5 responses), having competitive fire (4 responses), handling conflict (3 responses), and being passionate about current events (3 responses). One participant began her response,

I started out as a high school debater. I was very shy, quiet, and reserved. I had very few

friends. Joining the debate team in high school and participating in competition allowed me to realize that I was smart, and that I could be rewarded for being smart. Many girls that I went to high school with masked their intelligence so that they could date guys, or appear cool. For me, debate opened up an avenue for self-expression. After a year on the team, I became much more out-spoken and was able to excel in school. So, after years of debating and several years of coaching, I feel confident in my ideas, or at least know how to appear confident.

Another summed up, very simply, "It changed my life. Organized me in amazing ways."

Responses to the second prompt, which elicited commentary on the negative residue of debate experience, produced many more challenges and fewer topical clusters. One response dwarfed all others: participants reported that they speak too rapidly. Thirty-four participants admitted to this flaw, and twenty-three listed it first. Twenty-one participants reported that they were too argumentative, and twelve said they had unreasonable expectations of their students' abilities. No other response came from more than ten subjects, but the following appeared on more than five responses: impatient (with narrow-minded people, with slow talkers, with bad arguments, with slow thinkers, with slow-moving committee meetings), can't let things go, expect a winner in every conversation, rely too much on debate time management and wind up procrastinating, stop listening halfway through someone's statement once the point appears complete, criticize too much, missed college opportunities such as math and language classes, and overly analytical. Seven participants responded that debate experience had in no way hindered their work as educators. Two responses gather together many threads found in other contributions. One participant synthesized the problems debate can breed in educators' handling of the *substantive* end of their work:

Debate has a number of negative implications for the way participants evaluate scholarly

arguments. First, it puts a premium on extreme claims because those claims make for stronger impacts (whether in the causal or discursive sense). Second, it encourages an assumption that if "someone makes an argument" that provides a sufficient warrant for a claim. In both cases, debate can undermine effective evaluation of the strength and weaknesses of the internal arguments of scholarly work. Third, it can encourage superficial working knowledge of theories, approaches, and claims. Witness debate's engagement with post-structural argumentation in the middle 1990s. I think all of these deleterious impulses were things I had to overcome as I matured as a scholar.

Another wrote at length about interpersonal dynamics which are already found in academic communities, and cannot be laid entirely at the feet of debate, but clearly are fueled by some of debate's competitive excesses:

I think competition is, generally, a good thing. Nonetheless competitive atmospheres can occlude, perhaps sour, opportunities for collegiality and cooperation in an academic setting. For example, academic conferences need not be as "competitive" as they can occasionally be for me. Now, debate itself is not directly to blame for my framing of certain academic experiences. Nonetheless, there is (and has long been) a level of schadenfreude that obtains in the debate tournament experience, particularly at the national level, that has seeped from time to time in my digestion of conference experiences. Debate coaches through the years have a pretty poor record of fostering feelings of respect for others on the circuit. Their debaters, of course, emulate this manner of speech and, given the zero-sum nature of tournament competition and the natural neurosis attendant to the prospect of "loss" in this context, often find themselves saying sadistic things among their competitive allies about their opponents from other schools. In this context, competitors get arguments "shoved," "rammed," and

"smothered." Students are described as being "face-crushed" or "smacked-down." Now, all of this had been said many times before, and it is not my aim, simply, to echo this refrain. But I do often think that I could get more out of intellectual exchanges and public academic discussion if I had not spent 21 years on the circuit (6 as a competitor and 15 as a coach) thinking about how to dismantle other people's arguments and strategies. I think what I am really saying is that academia itself has more than a trace of sadism in the manner it conducts itself. The problem, essentially, is one of ego and anxiety. Debate is not to blame for any of it. Nonetheless, an extended immersion in debate tournament competition certainly has the potential to reinforce some of the nastier elements in academic life. I know it has in my case.

Likert item responses

On all seven proffered positive teaching behaviors, the mean response for the entire pool of participants was over 4, representing "Slightly Agree." The most popular answer was "I am good at thinking on my feet" ($M=4.85$, $SD=0.51$), and the least was "When I consider a major change in approach such as changing a course policy or adopting a new assignment, I am able to think of and prepare for all, or nearly all, likely student responses" ($M=4.19$, $SD=0.78$). The behavior most strongly tied to experience in debate, based on the followup prompt "If so, this is due entirely or in large part to my debate experience," was thinking on one's feet ($M=4.46$, $SD=0.66$), and the weakest was "I am confident dealing with disruptive behavior by students" ($M=3.34$, $SD=1.08$).

On the Likert items measuring negative teaching behaviors, the reported association was weaker, and the responses were more scattered. The strongest reported association was with the behavior, "I am impatient" ($M=3.56$, $SD=1.24$), and the weakest was "I frequently hurt a student's feelings by being excessively abrasive or confrontational" ($M=2.02$, $SD=1.21$). Interestingly,

when the numbers were broken out by academic field, people who taught political science and international relations pulled the mean up to 3.18, with six of eleven selecting "Slightly Agree" or "Strongly Agree." The follow-up prompt, tying negative classroom behaviors to previous debate experience, found the strongest linkage with "I speak so rapidly, my students struggle to keep up or to understand me all or a lot of the time" ($M=3.38$, $SD=1.13$), and the weakest with "I struggle at letting students participate in class because I enjoy doing most of the talking" ($M=2.64$, $SD=0.91$).

Discussion

Former debaters report that they have held on to the lessons of thinking rapidly and with rigor, and putting those thoughts into words, and doing so with extreme confidence. They are less unanimous on the leftover *bad* habits trained in by their experience in debate; very many of the responses to the open-ended question about negative behavior phrased it as "I *used* to" or "Debate is by no means bad, *but ...*" One participant confessed that he occasionally talks too fast, overstates conclusions in his research ("but heck, we all do that"), and is forceful in faculty meetings perhaps to excess, but concluded, "I really don't 'blame' debate for anything 'bad' that I do. In other words, the disadvantages are small and unimportant in my mind." The value of durable skills, the transformative experience of having grown into intellectual (and, in many cases, emotional) maturity through debate may move its alumni to defend it even against unspoken charges.

Few of the self-reported strengths and weaknesses are truly surprising. All of the Likert-scale items, even the ones with which few participants agreed, turned up as boasts or concerns spontaneously in a number of the responses to the open-ended items. A few were mildly unexpected, such as the positive effect of debate that it teaches one the acceptability (and inevitability) of defeat, and how to handle it gracefully. Three participants cited that lesson. On

the negative side, one participant mentioned that his time spent coaching forensics postponed the start of his more serious academic career, and several other participants spoke of other opportunity costs, including time-consuming coursework and other social and civic activities on campus. Several participants reported, in varying but related complaints, that their heightened efficiency, or research ability, or rapport with students, had actually bred tension with their colleagues, and that to have a truly collegial relationship they might be forced to hamstring themselves, or otherwise conceal the lessons they learned from debate.

The response from political science faculty is puzzling. It is unclear whether debaters who move into political science have more difficulty shedding the confrontational behaviors they pick up in debate, or whether political science students expect more relaxed interaction with their professors, or whether the sample size is so small that the finding is meaningless. For whatever reason, among this segment of political science professors who were once debaters, an ongoing problem of interpersonal tension and hurt feelings exists.

The dominant strengths of debate, according to educators who are former debaters, are the training in research, repeated exposure to speaking situations, and the building of confidence. The dominant problems are a struggle to slow down one's delivery, and a struggle not to be argumentative in all situations. Other strengths and weaknesses seem to be offshoots of this core. Debaters are highly efficient at producing knowledge and imposing order on information, but may be straitjacketed by a limited repertoire of thinking approaches. Debaters are thoughtful, disciplined and passionate, but in many cases struggle with empathy and fail again and again to listen to others complete a thought. Debaters have a wealth of illustrations, answer questions well, and make their classrooms into interactive, participatory encounters, but they also love their own voices, overlook nonlinear perspectives, and squash poorly conceived ideas so powerfully that they take a good deal of student self-esteem with them.

To say these observations are preliminary is an extreme understatement. The sample is heavily skewed toward men, and toward educators in the Communication field. Future research should attempt to even out those imbalances, and might also address the effects of high school debate on subsequent careers in education, as well as soliciting input from educators of younger students. But this study has identified some of the directions in which future work might proceed, some of the issues, both positive and negative, that might direct survey construction or matching of debate-instilled behaviors with recognized educator competencies.

Conclusion

With classrooms desperately in need of energetic, confident, efficient educators who are comfortable processing enormous volumes of information, who see through slogans and demagoguery, and who thrive on give-and-take and active learning, it can definitely be said that champion debaters are *not* destined for law school. Whatever the imperfections of debate, and there are many, its strengths as teaching preparation are too potent to be ignored any longer. The teaching profession beckons.

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